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PROBLEMS OF HUMANIZATION AND HUMANITARIZATION IN INSTITUTIONS OF HIGHER EDUCATION IN UKRAINE

In the process of updating and reforming education, the problems of the humanization and humanitarianization become more and more important. This is due to the low general cultural level of students of educational institutions, especially the technical profile, the weakening of intellectual and spiritual development, the spread of technocratic snobbery and the transfer of spiritual priorities to the periphery of the value orientations of students, which have become almost invisible against the background of a pragmatic worldview. All this is ultimately reflected in the level of professional culture of the future specialist and his professional qualities.

«The need for humanization and humanization of education is currently a subject of consensus in the educational environment. Dehumanization is seen primarily in the transformation of education into an instrumental category of industrial and market relations, in the loss of the meaning of education, as a result of which it turns into a utilitarian assimilation of a narrow range of professional knowledge and skills. Undoubtedly, the dehumanization of education is the result (illustration) of the dehumanization of social institutions. This process undermines the prospects of social development, narrows the horizons of democracy and levels spiritual and ethical values. The danger of dehumanized education lies in the fact that it is a factor of social instability, the distinctive features of which are not difficult to recognize in modern Ukraine» [1, p. 190–191].

Utilitarianism reveals a person's dependence on generally accepted norms of perception, which are applied in a disciplinary manner, reveal the subjection of an individual to something independent of him. Spirituality, on the contrary, reveals the ability of a person to harmonize his unique with the generally accepted, to "found" himself as an integral part of the surrounding reality, turning this reality into a self-dependent existence. This provision should be taken into account when addressing the processes of formation of spiritual culture in the pedagogical process along with the task of formation of developed human sensibility. After all, everyday consciousness usually considers sensual pleasure, identifying it with animal experiences and pleasures, limiting sensuality to the direct opposite of spiritual. At the same time, the spiritual begins to be understood exclusively as a worldview, built on the ascetic negation of the sensual as pleasure, rather than its enrichment and diversification.

«Humanization of education is a systemic problem – a problem of theory and practice and must be developed on a completely new basis, the essence of which is to turn to a human-creative model of education. ...The humanization of education should be understood not only at the creative level, but also at the level of modern constructive practical developments, which

provide for a system of normative knowledge oriented to various subjects of activity. Today, real education, in connection with the accession of Ukraine to the Bologna concept, creates a deficit of humanitarian culture, which leads to spiritual decline... » [1, p. 190].

The urgent need to intensify the process of forming the spiritual culture of student youth, sociological research of this problem is due, not least, to the low general cultural level of students of technical educational institutions. Many of them are characterized by a low language culture, the inability to clearly and competently formulate their thoughts, work with scientific literature, an undeveloped ability to self-criticize, and the need for self-education and self-upbringing. The underdevelopment of aesthetic culture is also manifested in the weakening of intellectual and spiritual development, in the spread of technocratic snobbery. All this is ultimately reflected in the level of professional culture of the future specialist, in his qualities as a professional employee.

Most philosophers of the 20th century. saw a pernicious danger for human existence in modern technologism and technocratism (V. Weidle, M. Heidegger, J. Maritain, M. Berdyaev, G. Marcel, etc.). After all, technocratism leads, in their opinion, to a crisis of art. Therefore, «... the most practical significance for reforming the education system is the axiological aspect of the new paradigm of education - a new system of values and ethical relations between teacher and pupil, teacher and student.

The central value is, of course, the person, the personality, since the development of its potential, the process of creative self-actualization is the absolute goal of both social development and the functioning of the education system» [1, p. 192]. This provision on personality is contained in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and therefore it «...presupposes the priority of humanitarian values of the education system. It is their development that determines the process of humanization and humanitarianization of education at the current stage – as the main direction of meaningful reform of the education system. Two aspects become crucial.

The first involves not only the formation of a certain system of knowledge, but also the development of spirituality in the context of the harmonious interaction of all individual processes of world perception. ...The second aspect focuses on overcoming the technocratic nature of modern education. ...The main task that arises in the context of the needs of humanitarianization of education is the mutual enrichment and mutual complementation of knowledge from individual subjects, which should contribute to the creation of a systemic image of the world. Such education should be aimed at the development of heuristic and creative knowledge, experience of creative activity» [1, p. 192].

The system-forming principle of formation and presentation of educational material in accordance with the requirements of a spiritually developed person is an aspect approach that combines the principles of reflection and creative transformation of the content of the subject of knowledge [2, p. 34–41]. In the pedagogical literature, there are different opinions regarding the means of achieving the spiritual development of the individual in the educational process of higher education of the institution. Subjects that purposefully form the spiritual culture of a student's personality are traditionally considered educational disciplines of the socio-humanitarian cycle. «The vocation of the humanitarian component of education needs a thorough understanding. The effectiveness of teaching humanitarian disciplines is directly dependent on the level of their conceptual unity. It should be based on awareness of the

fundamental problems of the methodology of scientific knowledge, methods of pedagogical innovations and philosophical understanding of truth. In general, it is difficult to overestimate the mission of the humanitarian block of education in the formation of a worldview, value orientations, the general culture of an individual and his civic position - it is obviously unique» [1, p. 192–193].

Some researchers claim that all subjects of the humanitarian cycle contain spiritual potential. And subjects of a natural and scientific nature are completely far from aesthetics in the modern educational process. But in the training plan of future specialists, not enough time is allocated for their proper and high-quality study of subjects of the social and humanitarian cycle. In technical institutions of higher education, social and humanitarian disciplines are optimized, combined, and classroom hours are reduced. Therefore, a dilemma arises: on one hand, there is a need of modern society for a spiritually developed personality, and on the other hand, there is an acute shortage of study time in the educational process of higher education institutions. The solution to this problem can be seen in the rethinking of the traditional approach to the educational process. The humanization of education should contribute to overcoming the artificial separation of narrow professional natural, economic, and technical-technological knowledge from the humanities. After all, the example of Chernobyl shows that this catastrophe was not so much man-made as humanitarian, both in terms of consequences and causes.

Culture, its subject forms, spirituality, as well as the human community are carriers of the forms of perception and understanding of the world. An individual person masters such forms individually in socially reproduced activity, communication, in a specific process of socialization and learning. Outside the world culture and communication, subject-subject relationship, these generic human properties do not develop in an individual. In other words, the method of transmission of a person's ancestral properties is sociocultural, not genetic or biological, as in animals. Another way out of the current situation is the creation of a system implemented in European countries. Its essence is to support national culture and restrain pirated, foreign products through the appropriate tax policy, which stimulates the development of domestic book publishing, music, and culture in general and creates stricter conditions for the export of foreign products of mass culture.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the problems of humanization and humanitarianization in higher education institutions of Ukraine are systemic and should be carefully considered and resolved both at the level of the Ministry of Education of Ukraine and at the level of higher education institutions. For a purposeful process of forming a student who is able not only to perceive the beautiful from the standpoint of a spiritual ideal, but also to live and create according to the laws of beauty, it is necessary to turn to the model of education, where the main problem will be a creative, harmoniously developed personality.

References

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